

A following association between a bluefin trevally (*Caranx melampygus*) and geometric moray eel (*Gymnothorax griseus*) at Mahé, Seychelles, and a review of eels as nuclear species in fish foraging associations

Michael R. Crossland and Sheau Fong Chan

Introduction

Interspecific foraging associations are widespread among marine fish, particularly in reef ecosystems. One of the most common types is the ‘nuclear-follower’ association, in which the foraging activity of one species (the nuclear species) exposes hidden prey that are then consumed by follower species (Lukoschek and McCormick, 2000; Sazima et al., 2007; Sabino et al., 2016; Ternes et al., 2018). It is generally thought that such associations do not benefit the nuclear species and may, in at least some instances, be disadvantageous due to loss of prey items to follower individuals (Lukoschek and McCormick, 2000; Sazima et al., 2007; Craig and Erisman, 2010). Nonetheless, nuclear-follower associations have long been noted by marine researchers (e.g. Hobson, 1974; Montgomery, 1975; Ormond, 1980) and likely play an important role in the trophic ecology of reef fishes (Ormond, 1980; Strand, 1988; Sazima et al., 2006, 2007; Sabino et al., 2016).

Most nuclear species are diurnal carnivores (occasionally, herbivores) that forage in the benthos by disturbing the substrate or exploring crevices and refugia (Lukoschek and McCormick, 2000; Sazima et al., 2007). Additionally, most nuclear species are fish, although this role can also be played by other organisms such as octopuses, sea-stars, brittle stars, urchins and turtles (Strand, 1988; Gibran, 2007; Sazima et al., 2007; Moore and Auster, 2009; Bayley and Rose, 2020; Somaweera and Somaweera, 2021). In many instances, the commencement of a nuclear-follower interaction is opportunistic, with followers locating nuclear species via physical disturbance of substrate caused by the latter, or by visual features of the nuclear species itself (Krajewski, 2009). Auditory foraging cues may also play a role in location of some nuclear species (Pryor and Milton, 2021). However, some follower species actively seek out non-feeding nuclear species (e.g. resting nuclear moray eels) and use body signals to prompt the non-feeding nuclear species to commence foraging and, once foraging has commenced, further indicate the location of any escaped prey to the nuclear species (Bshari et al., 2006; Vail et al., 2013). Thus, nuclear-follower associations can be either passive or interactive.

Associations that involve one or two individuals of a nuclear species and a small number of follower individuals are termed ‘attendant associations’ (Lukoschek and McCormick, 2000). Attendant associations can be divided into four categories: (1) following and scavenging, (2) co-operative hunting, (3) hunting by riding (using the nuclear species as cover to access prey), and (4) hunting by aggressive mimicry (mimicking a harmless nuclear species); of these, following and scavenging is the most common (Ormond, 1980; Lukoschek and McCormick, 2000). Pereira et al. (2012) further divided the following and scavenging category into two subcategories: ephemeral feeding associations versus following feeding associations, the former lasting < 5 minutes with the follower species not moving outside its territory, and the latter lasting >5 minutes with the follower species moving outside its territory to continue the interaction. More recently, Pryor and Milton (2021) described an additional subcategory of attendant association among reef fishes: ‘scavenging at anvil’ which refers to foraging associations triggered by tool use of the nuclear fish species.

In this paper, we describe a following association between a bluefin trevally (*Caranx melampygus*; Family Carangidae) and a geometric moray eel (*Gymnothorax griseus*; Family Muraedidae) in inshore waters of Mahé, the Republic of Seychelles (hereafter referred to as Seychelles). We also conducted a literature review of nuclear-follower associations involving reef fish where eels are the nuclear species to assist interpret our observations and confirm their novelty.

Methods

Study species

The geometric moray eel occurs in shallow coastal waters on coral and rocky reefs throughout tropical regions of the Western Indian Ocean (Froese and Pauly, 2024). It is a solitary species known to hunt diurnally, searching for food amongst fissures and cracks in the reef structure (Karplus, 1978; Diamant and Shpigel, 1985; Shpigel and Fishelson, 1989; Randall and Golani, 1995; Naumann and Wild, 2013). The bluefin trevally is a diurnal reef-associated species that occurs widely throughout tropical regions of the Indo-Pacific (Froese and Pauly, 2024). It is primarily piscivorous but also feeds on crustaceans (Hobson, 1974; Potts, 1980, 1981; Froese and Pauly, 2024).

Field observations

Our observations were made at Fairyland Beach, Anse Royale, Mahé, Seychelles on 20 May 2024 while snorkelling approximately 160 m from the shoreline in water of about 2.5 m depth (04°44'14"S, 55°31'27"E); (Figure 1). The habitat was a mix of open sandy substrate, sandy substrate with seagrass (*Oceana* [= *Cymodocea*] *serrulata*) attached to the sand, and patches of large brown algae (*Sargassum* spp.) attached either to the sand or to

small patches of coral and rock. We photographed our observations and used the image metadata to determine the specific timing of events described below.

Literature review

The most recent review of eels as nuclear species in follower associations among reef fish was conducted by Ternes et al. (2018). That review used the search tools Scopus and Google Scholar and the search terms ‘follower + fish + eel’, ‘nuclear + follower + reef fish’ and ‘following + behaviour’ (Ternes et al., 2018). We repeated this search protocol using the same search tools and terms for the years subsequent to that study (i.e. from 2018 to 2024). In addition, we used the same search terms in Web of Science from inception to 2024 in case any papers were missed in the Scopus or Google Scholar searches. Except for one paper (see Results), we read all relevant papers retrieved, including all papers cited in Ternes et al. (2018). We also read any papers cited in the retrieved papers but not found directly during our online searches.

Results

Field observations

On 20 May at 10:41:14 am (hr:min:sec), we observed a single geometric moray eel (*G. griseus*, estimated total length TL = 40 cm) from a distance of ~ 10 m. The eel was slowly swimming immediately above open sandy substrate and did not appear to be foraging (Figure 2). Two fish were closely associated with the eel. The first fish was a bluefin trevally (*C. melampygus*, estimated TL = 20 cm) positioned < 5 cm directly above the dorsal mid-section of the eel (Figure 2). We tentatively identified the second fish as a thumbprint emperor (*Lethrinus harak*, estimated TL = 25 cm). This fish was positioned parallel to the left side of the eel at a distance of about 25 cm, just above the substrate (Figure 2). As we slowly approached along the water surface, the thumbprint emperor swam away but the bluefin trevally remained. The eel stopped on the substratum at 10:41:25 am and turned to face us while the trevally slowly swam around the eel (Figure 3a). At 10:42:34 am, the eel moved into a coiled body position on the substratum, still facing us, while the trevally continued to slowly swim around and above the eel, sometimes becoming temporarily stationary (Figures 3b-d). At all times, the trevally remained within 30 cm of the eel. At 10:42:47 am, the eel quickly swam along the substratum to a small patch of *Sargassum* spp. ~ 2 m away, with the trevally following immediately. Both species disappeared completely within the *Sargassum* spp. patch. We waited on the water surface for a further two minutes, after which time neither species had emerged, so we swam away. We did not see any agonistic interaction between the trevally and eel during our observations.

While snorkelling in the same general location between 9:00 am to 10:00 am that same morning, we also saw several fish species actively foraging in the sandy substrate (four yellowstripe goatfish, *Mulloidichthys flavolineatus*, estimated TL = 20 cm; three dash-and-

dot goatfish, *Parupeneus barberinus*, estimated TL = 15 cm; three bluetail mullet, *Crenimugil buehanani*, estimated TL = 30 cm). We also saw a single starry moray eel (*Echidna nebulosa*, estimated TL = 40 cm) slowly swimming within 5 cm of the sandy substrate, apparently not feeding. None of these species were being followed by other fish species.

Literature review

The review of Ternes et al. (2018) identified nineteen published studies documenting eels as the nuclear species being followed by other fish species. Our review has increased this to 28 previously published studies (Table 1). There was only one of these 28 publications that we could not access: Fricke (1972). However, given that the species association details for this paper are cited consistently in four papers that we did read (Karplus, 1978; Ormond, 1980; Diamant and Shpigel, 1985; Randall and Golani, 1995), we include Fricke (1972) in our table (Table 1). We found only two studies published since the review of Ternes et al. (2018): Auster et al. (2019) and Inagaki et al. (2020).

Most eel-fish following association studies have been conducted in the Atlantic Ocean (54%, fifteen studies) followed by the Indian Ocean (25%, seven studies) and the Pacific Ocean (21%, six studies). Our study is the eighth study for the Indian Ocean, and the first nuclear-follower association reported for any species of eel as the nuclear species for Seychelles, with all other nuclear eel studies in the Indian Ocean having been conducted in the Red Sea (Table 1).

Including our observations, a total of 89 species combinations of eel (nuclear) – fish (follower) associations have now been described (Table 1). For 63 of these associations, the nuclear eel was a moray eel (Family Muraenidae; eleven known eel species, twelve records of unidentified moray eel species), while for 26 associations the nuclear eel was a snake eel (Family Ophichthidae; two known eel species, one unidentified species of *Myrichthys*). Follower fish comprised 64 species from eighteen families, dominated by the Epinephelidae (33% of all records, Table 2). We note that, in some instances, authors of previous studies were not always explicit in describing the species being observed. For example, Montgomery (1975) initially described *Mycteroperca rosacea* following ‘morays’ (identified by that author as *Gymnothorax castaneus*) but thereafter reported observations of various fish species following ‘morays’ with the eel species not specified, making us unsure whether these subsequent observations refer to *G. castaneus* (since this was previously described as ‘moray’ by that author) or instead refer to unidentified moray species. For the purposes of our current review, we labelled an eel species as ‘unidentified’ if it was not explicitly identified in the original paper (Table 1).

Only four of the previous studies report fish from the Family Carangidae as followers of nuclear eels (Table 1). Two of these studies involved bluefin trevally (*C. melampygus*) as the follower species: Quimbayo et al. (2014) reported *C. melampygus* following a finespotted moray (*G. dovii*) in Colombia, while Auster et al. (2019) reported *C. melampygus*

in a feeding association (likely a following association) with an unidentified Muraenid eel in Costa Rica. None of the previous 28 studies report *C. melampygius* following a geometric moray eel (*G. griseus*; Table 1).

We also note that several of the eel-fish follower associations listed in Table 3 of the Ternes et al. (2018) review are not included in our Table 1. We explain these discrepancies as follows. Firstly, Ternes et al. (2018) list five fish species as being involved in a nuclear-follower association with the spotted moray eel *Gymnothorax moringa*: *Acanthurus bahianus*, *Bodianus rufus*, *Chaetodon capistratus*, *Holacanthus tricolor* and *Scarus taeniopterus*. The reference cited by Ternes et al. (2018) for these species associations is Dubin (1982). However, Dubin classifies the interaction between each of these five species and *G. moringa* as ‘rubbing and posing’, not ‘following’, the latter being a separate category used by Dubin for other fish species associated with eels. It is true that visual signals could potentially be used by follower species to initiate a nuclear-follower interaction as has been demonstrated in other fish species (e.g. Bshari et al., 2006). However, this possibility is not speculated by Dubin. Also, in instances where fish use body posture or gestures to initiate a following interaction, the displaying fish has broad diet overlap with the nuclear species (Bshari et al., 2006); consequently, prey that escape from the hunting nuclear species are viable food items for the following species. However, Dubin (1982) notes that the five fish species listed above displaying rubbing and posing interactions with *G. moringa* have no diet overlap with this eel species. In contrast, other fish species classified by Dubin as having follower associations with eels have extensive diet overlap with the nuclear eel species. Dubin speculates that a possible reason for the rubbing and posing behaviour of these five fish species could be to dislodge eels (a potential predator) from refugia to allow the fish to safely rest while inactive during the night. For these reasons, we excluded *A. bahianus*, *B. rufus*, *C. capistratus*, *H. tricolor* and *S. taeniopterus* as forming a nuclear-follower association with *G. moringa* in our table (Table 1).

Additionally, there were some nuclear-follower associations listed in Table 3 of Ternes et al. (2018) that we could not find when we read the original citations, and so we excluded these from Table 1: *Gymnothorax javanicus* followed by *Epinephelus fasciatus* (reference cited: Diamant and Shpigel, 1988; note, correct year is 1985), *Myrichthys breviceps* followed by *Cephalopholis fulva* (references cited: Sazima et al., 2007; Araújo et al., 2009; Maia-Nogueira et al., 2009) and *Myrichthys ocellatus* followed by *Epinephelus adscensionis* (reference cited: Gasparini and Floeter, 2001). Finally, Table 3 of Ternes et al. (2018) cites Araújo et al. (2009) for *Myrichthys ocellatus* followed by *Mycteroperca acutirostris*. However, Araújo et al. cite Gibran (2007) for this association and do not provide any additional personal observations for this species combination. Hence, we also excluded Araújo et al. (2009) as a reference for *Myrichthys ocellatus* followed by *Mycteroperca acutirostris* in Table 1.

Discussion

We observed a bluefin trevally (*C. melampygyus*) in a close following association with a geometric moray eel (*G. griseus*) in inshore waters of Mahé, Seychelles. Although the eel did not appear to be foraging at the time, several factors point to this being a nuclear-follower association (most likely, foraging and scavenging): (1) the bluefin trevally was in very close proximity to the eel without any aggressive interactions, and a foraging association is the most likely explanation for such prolonged close proximity, (2) eels commonly function as nuclear species in interspecific foraging associations (Table 1), (3) Carangid species (including *C. melampygyus*) are known to form nuclear-follower associations as followers with a variety of other fish species, including eels (Tables 1 and 3), and (4) follower fish species trail nuclear species such as moray eels not only during foraging events but also between foraging events (Dubin, 1982; Strand, 1988). Thus, we conclude the interaction we observed was likely a nuclear-follower association between foraging events. Based on our literature review, this is the first record of a nuclear-follower association between *G. griseus* and *C. melampygyus* in any geographic region worldwide (Table 1). To our knowledge, it is also the first record of a nuclear-follower association involving an eel (of any species) as the nuclear species in Seychelles, with all other nuclear eel studies in the Indian Ocean having been conducted in the Red Sea (Table 1). The only other reports of *C. melampygyus* as a follower species in Seychelles are from Aldabra Atoll and involve *C. melampygyus* following a variety of non-eel reef fish species (Table 3). As a general comment, we note that the reporting of a new single species combination for a nuclear-follower association, such as we present here, may not seem particularly impactful. However, numerous papers cited in our literature review are precisely this: reports of one or a few fish species following a single nuclear eel species (Karplus, 1978; Gerhardinger et al., 2006; Maia-Nogueira et al. 2009; Craig and Erisman, 2010; Naumann and Wild, 2013). Such observations, albeit at times brief research notes, are valuable because the accumulation of such data allows a more comprehensive review of nuclear-follower associations (e.g. Ternes et al., 2018; present study).

The bluefin trevally we observed following the geometric moray eel was a small individual, which is consistent with observations that small individuals of bluefin trevally are more likely to form interspecific foraging associations than large individuals of this species (Potts, 1980, 1981). The association we observed lasted for a minimum of 1 minute 33 seconds, which is not unusual in that nuclear-follower associations can last from as little as 20 seconds to >1 hour (Karplus, 1978; Sazima and Grossman, 2005; Naumann and Wild, 2013; Pereira et al., 2021; Sorgon and Abesamis, 2023). However, because we do not know precisely when the association started or finished, we cannot distinguish whether our observation constitutes an ephemeral attendant association or a following attendant association (*sensu* Pereira et al., 2012).

In addition to the *G. griseus*, we saw another non-foraging eel species (starry moray eel, *E. nebulosa*) swimming slowly across the sandy substrate, as well as three other fish species (yellowstripe goatfish, *M. flavolineatus*; dash-and-dot goatfish, *P. barberinus*; bluetail mullet, *C. buchanani*) actively foraging and disturbing the sandy substrate. However, none of these fish had follower species associated with them. In other geographic locations, bluefin trevally have been recorded to form nuclear-follower associations (as followers) with a variety of fish, including other muraenid eel species and yellowstripe goatfish (Tables 1 and 3). The lack of following associations for the starry moray eel, yellowstripe goatfish, dash-and-dot goatfish or bluetail mullet during our observations may be due to one or more factors. Firstly, the duration of nuclear-follower associations among reef fish can be very brief, sometimes less than two minutes (Sazima and Grossman, 2005; Pereira et al., 2021; Sorgon and Abesamis, 2023). Thus, by chance we may have missed such associations with these other species, and indeed, we may have been lucky to have observed the bluefin trevally following the geometric eel. Additionally, follower fish can be very selective in choosing which nuclear species they follow (Hobson, 1974; Strand, 1988), as well as which particular individual within a nuclear species they follow (Vail et al., 2014). Any of these factors may have played a role in the absence of follower fish species for the starry moray eel, yellowstripe goatfish, dash-and-dot goatfish and bluetail mullet at the time of our observations.

Data for nuclear-follower associations among reef fish in Seychelles are apparently rare, with the only previous records identified in our literature search being Potts (1980, 1981) who conducted studies at Aldabra Atoll in the Outer Islands of Seychelles. Given the widespread nature of eel-fish nuclear associations in the Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Oceans (Table 1), we suspect these interactions are more common in Seychelles than currently documented. We encourage the publication of such observations to improve the understanding of local reef ecosystems.

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Dr Michael Crossland is a Research Affiliate with The University of Sydney, Australia. He has a broad interest in marine, freshwater and terrestrial ecology and has published 72 peer-reviewed scientific papers.

michael.crossland@sydney.edu.au

Sheau Fong Chan is an amateur naturalist with an interest in marine and freshwater ecology. She has published 1 peer-reviewed scientific paper.

Figure 1: Location of field observations, Fairyland Beach, Mahé, Republic of Seychelles
(White pin indicates location of observations)

Inset map source: Google Earth, available at <https://earth.google.com/web> [Accessed 25 August 2024]

*Figure 2: Initial sighting of geometric moray eel (*G. griseus*, a), bluefin trevally (*C. melampygus*, b) and thumbprint emperor (*L. harak*, c)*

Figure 3: Geometric moray eel (*G. griseus*) turns to face the authors with the bluefin trevally (*C. melampygus*) in attendance (a), geometric moray eel assumes a coiled body posture with the bluefin trevally remaining in attendance (b, c, d)

Table 1: Follower-feeding associations between eels as the nuclear species and other fish as the follower species in marine habitat, as identified in our literature review. Also included is the observation from the present study. Taxonomy updated according to Froese and Pauly (2024) except for *Lycodontis* sp. because this eel as cited by Diamant and Shpigel (1985) has four current valid genera which we cannot choose between. Original species names listed in cited reference are as follows: ¹*Balistes verres*, ²*Epinephelus panamensis*, ³*Carangoides bartholomaei*, ⁴*Siderea grisea*, ⁵*Cephalopholis miniatus*, ⁶*Scorpaenopsis gibbosus*, ⁷*Lycodontis javanicus*, ⁸*Muraena miliaris*, ⁹*Epinephelus cruentatum* (*E. cruentatus*), ¹⁰*Epinephelus fulvus*, ¹¹*Epinephelus cifuentesi*, ¹²*Myrichthys acuminatus*, ¹³*Mycteroperca marginata*, ¹⁴*Eucinostomus lefroyi*, ¹⁵*Stephanolepis hispidus*

Nuclear eel species	Nuclear eel common name	Follower species Family	Follower species	Follower species common name	Location	Reference
Muraenidae						
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Panamic green moray	Balistidae	<i>Sufflamen verres</i> ¹	Orangeside Triggerfish	Mexico	Strand 1988
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Panamic green moray	Grammistidae	<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	Mottled soapfish	Mexico	Strand 1988
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Panamic green moray	Labridae	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Mexican hogfish	Mexico	Strand 1988
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Panamic green moray	Pomacanthidae	<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	King angelfish	Mexico	Strand 1988
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Panamic green moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Starry grouper	Mexico	Strand 1988
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Panamic green moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i> ²	Pacific graysby	Mexico	Strand 1988

<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Panamic green moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Mycteroperca rosacea</i>	Leopard grouper	Mexico	Montgomery 1975, Strand 1988
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Finespotted moray	Aulostomidae	<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	Chinese trumpetfish	Colombia	Quimbayo et al. 2014
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Finespotted moray	Carangidae	<i>Caranx melampyngus</i>	Bluefin trevally	Colombia	Quimbayo et al. 2014
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Finespotted moray	Carangidae	<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Longfin yellowtail	Colombia	Quimbayo et al. 2014
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Finespotted moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Leather bass	Colombia	Quimbayo et al. 2014
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Finespotted moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Sailfin grouper	Colombia	Quimbayo et al. 2014
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Finespotted moray	Labridae	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Mexican hogfish	Colombia	Quimbayo et al. 2014
<i>Gymnothorax funebris</i>	Green moray	Carangidae	<i>Caranx bartholomaei</i> ³	Yellow jack	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Gymnothorax funebris</i>	Green moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i>	Coney	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Sabino et al. 2016, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i>	Geometric moray	Carangidae	<i>Caranx melampyngus</i>	Bluefin trevally	Seychelles	Present study
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Aethaloperca rogaea</i>	Redmouth grouper	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis argus</i>	Peacock hind	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985, Shpigel and Fishelson 1989

<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis hemistiktos</i>	Yellowfin hind	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985, Shpigel and Fishelson 1989
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis miniata</i> ⁵	Coral hind	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985, Shpigel and Fishelson 1989
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus fasciatus</i>	Blacktip grouper	Red Sea	Karplus 1978, Diamant and Shpigel 1985
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Variola louti</i>	Yellow-edged lyretail	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Grammistidae	<i>Grammistes sexlineatus</i>	Goldenstriped soapfish	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i>	Geometric moray	Labridae	<i>Thalassoma rueppellii</i>	Klunzinger's wrasse	Red Sea	Karplus 1978
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Mullidae	<i>Parupeneus cyclostomus</i>	Gold-saddle goatfish	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Scorpaenidae	<i>Pterois volitans</i>	Red lionfish	Red Sea	Karplus 1978, Diamant and Shpigel 1985, Naumann and Wild 2013
<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i> ⁴	Geometric moray	Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaenopsis gibbosa</i> ⁶	Humpbacked scorpionfish	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i> ⁷	Giant moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis argus</i>	Peacock hind	Red Sea	Fricke 1972*
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Giant moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Plectropomus leopardus</i>	Leopard coral grouper	Red Sea	Vail et al. 2013

<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Giant moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Plectropomus pessuliferus</i>	Roving coral grouper	Red Sea	Bshary et al. 2006, Vail et al. 2013
<i>Gymnothorax miliaris</i> ⁸	Goldentail moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis cruentata</i> ⁹	Graysby	Barbados, U.S. Virgin Islands	Dubin 1982, Abrams et al. 1983
<i>Gymnothorax miliaris</i> ⁸	Goldentail moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i> ¹⁰	Coney	Barbados	Dubin 1982
<i>Gymnothorax miliaris</i> ⁸	Goldentail moray	Grammistidae	<i>Rypticus saponaceus</i>	Greater soapfish	Barbados	Dubin 1982
<i>Gymnothorax moringa</i>	Spotted moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis cruentata</i> ⁹	Graysby	Barbados, U.S. Virgin Islands	Dubin 1982, Abrams et al. 1983
<i>Gymnothorax moringa</i>	Spotted moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i> ¹⁰	Coney	Barbados	Dubin 1982
<i>Gymnothorax ocellatus</i>	Ocellated moray	Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus</i> spp.	Snapper	Brazil	Santos and Castro 2003
<i>Gymnothorax ocellatus</i>	Ocellated moray	Serranidae	<i>Diplectrum</i> spp.	Sand perch	Brazil	Santos and Castro 2003
<i>Gymnothorax vicinus</i>	Purplemouth moray	Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus coeruleus</i>	Blue tang surgeonfish	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Gymnothorax vicinus</i>	Purplemouth moray	Carangidae	<i>Caranx bartholomaei</i> ³	Yellow jack	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Gymnothorax vicinus</i>	Purplemouth moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i>	Coney	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Gymnothorax vicinus</i>	Purplemouth moray	Haemulidae	<i>Haemulon parra</i>	Sailor's grunt	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020

<i>Gymnothorax vicinus</i>	Purplemouth moray	Labridae	<i>Halichoeres radiatus</i>	Puddingwife wrasse	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Gymnothorax vicinus</i>	Purplemouth moray	Mullidae	<i>Pseudupeneus maculatus</i>	Spotted goatfish	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Lycodontis</i> sp.	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus fasciatus</i>	Blacktip grouper	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Jewel moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	Pacific mutton hamlet	Mexico	Craig and Erisman 2010
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Jewel moray	Serranidae	<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	Barred serrano	Mexico	Craig and Erisman 2010
<i>Muraena pavonina</i>	Whitespot moray	Carangidae	<i>Caranx latus</i>	Horse-eye jack	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Muraena pavonina</i>	Whitespot moray	Carangidae	<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Black jack	Brazil	Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Muraena pavonina</i>	Whitespot moray	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i>	Coney	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Muraena pavonina</i>	Whitespot moray	Labridae	<i>Halichoeres radiatus</i>	Puddingwife wrasse	Brazil	Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Muraena pavonina</i>	Whitespot moray	Labrisomidae	<i>Labrisomus conditus</i>	Masquerader hairy blenny	Brazil	Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Muraena pavonina</i>	Whitespot moray	Labrisomidae	<i>Labrisomus</i> cf. <i>nuchipinnis</i>	Hairy blenny	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Carangidae	<i>Caranx melampygyus</i>	Bluefin trevally	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Carcharhinidae	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Whitetip reef shark	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019

Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis cruentata</i> ⁹	Graysby	U.S. Virgin Islands	Abrams et al. 1983
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	Pacific graysby	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Leather bass	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Starry grouper	Mexico	Montgomery 1975
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i> ¹¹	Olive grouper	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2016
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Sailfin grouper	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Mycteroperca rosacea</i>	Leopard grouper	Mexico	Montgomery 1975
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Labridae	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Mexican hogfish	Mexico	Montgomery 1975
Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	Yellow snapper	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019

Ophichthidae

<i>Myrichthys breviceps</i> ¹²	Sharptail eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i> ¹⁰	Coney	Barbados, Brazil	Dubin 1982, Gasparini and Floeter 2001
<i>Myrichthys breviceps</i>	Sharptail eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus adscensionis</i>	Rock hind	Brazil	Gasparini and Floeter 2001
<i>Myrichthys breviceps</i> ¹²	Sharptail eel	Serranidae	<i>Hypoplectrus puella</i>	Barred hamlet	Barbados	Dubin 1982

<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Acanthuridae	<i>Acanthurus bahianus</i>	Barber surgeonfish	Brazil	Pereira et al. 2012
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis fulva</i>	Coney	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Araújo et al. 2009, Maia-Nogueira et al. 2009, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus adscensionis</i>	Rock hind	Brazil	Araújo et al. 2009, Maia-Nogueira et al. 2009
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i> ¹³	Dusky grouper	Brazil	Gerhardinger et al. 2006, Gibran 2007, Luiz Jr et al. 2008
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Mycteroperca acutirostris</i>	Comb grouper	Brazil	Gibran 2007, Ternes et al. 2018
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Mycteroperca bonaci</i>	Black grouper	Brazil	Maia-Nogueira et al. 2009
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Gerreidae	<i>Ulaema lefroyi</i> ¹⁴	Mottled mojarra	Brazil	Araújo et al. 2009
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Grammistidae	<i>Rypticus bistrispinus</i>	Freckled soapfish	Brazil	Maia-Nogueira et al. 2009
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labridae	<i>Bodianus pulchellus</i>	Spotfin hogfish	Brazil	Ternes et al. 2018
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labridae	<i>Bodianus rufus</i>	Spanish hogfish	Brazil	Ternes et al. 2018
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labridae	<i>Halichoeres brasiliensis</i>	Brazilian wrasse	Brazil	Araújo et al. 2009, Ternes et al. 2018

<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labridae	<i>Halichoeres poeyi</i>	Blackear wrasse	Brazil	Pereira et al. 2012, Chaves et al. 2013, Ternes et al. 2018
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labridae	<i>Halichoeres radiatus</i>	Puddingwife wrasse	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labridae	<i>Thalassoma noronhanum</i>	Noronha wrasse	Brazil	Sazima et al. 2007, Inagaki et al. 2020
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labrisomidae	<i>Labrisomus cricota</i>	Mock blenny	Brazil	Pereira et al. 2012
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Labrisomidae	<i>Labrisomus nuchipinnis</i>	Hairy blenny	Brazil	Pereira et al. 2012, Chaves et al. 2013
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus alexandrei</i>	Brazilian snapper	Brazil	Araújo et al. 2009
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Monacanthidae	<i>Stephanolepis hispida</i> ¹⁵	Planehead filefish	Brazil	Ternes et al. 2018
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Pomacentridae	<i>Stegastes fuscus</i>	Brazilian damsel	Brazil	Pereira et al. 2012
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Pomacentridae	<i>Stegastes variabilis</i>	Cocoa damselfish	Brazil	Pereira et al. 2012
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Serranidae	<i>Serranus baldwini</i>	Lantern bass	Brazil	Ternes et al. 2018
<i>Myrichthys ocellatus</i>	Goldspotted eel	Serranidae	<i>Serranus flaviventris</i>	Twinspot bass	Brazil	Maia-Nogueira et al. 2009
<i>Myrichthys</i> sp.	Snake eel	Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus fasciatus</i>	Blacktip grouper	Red Sea	Diamant and Shpigel 1985

*Reference not seen by authors of current study but cited in Karplus (1978), Ormond (1980), Diamant and Shpigel (1985) and Randall and Golani (1995)

Table 2: Number and percent of fish species (per Family) as followers of eels in nuclear-follower associations, as identified in our literature review

Follower Family	Number of species	% of species total
Epinephelidae	21	32.8
Labridae	8	12.5
Carangidae	5	7.8
Serranidae	5	7.8
Grammistidae	4	6.3
Labrisomidae	3	4.7
Lutjanidae	3	4.7
Acanthuridae	2	3.1
Mullidae	2	3.1
Pomacentridae	2	3.1
Scorpaenidae	2	3.1
Aulostomidae	1	1.6
Balistidae	1	1.6
Carcharhinidae	1	1.6
Gerridae	1	1.6
Haemulidae	1	1.6
Monacanthidae	1	1.6
Pomacanthidae	1	1.6
Total	64	100

Table 3: Foraging associations where bluefin trevally (*Caranx melampyngus*) follow other fish species, as identified in our literature review. Also included is the observation from the present study. Taxonomy updated according to Froese and Pauly (2024). Original species names listed in cited reference are as follows: ¹*Gaterin harrawayi*, ²*Mulloidichthys samoensis*, ³*Parupeneus chryserydros*, ⁴*Pseudupeneus macronema*, ⁵*Paranthias colonus*, ⁶*Manta birostris*. ‘Hunting by riding’ refers to the follower species (in this case, *C. melampyngus*) using the nuclear species as cover to approach prey (Ormond, 1980; Lukoschek and McCormick, 2000)

Foraging association type and follower species	Nuclear species Family	Nuclear species	Nuclear species common name	Location	Reference
Following and scavenging					
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Balistidae	<i>Balistoides viridescens</i>	Titan triggerfish	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Carangidae	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Giant trevally	Seychelles	Potts 1981
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Carcharhinidae	<i>Carcharhinus melanopterus</i>	Blacktip reef shark	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Dasyatidae	<i>Dasyatis</i> sp.	Stingray	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Epinephelidae	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Leather bass	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Haemulidae	<i>Plectorhinchus albobittatus</i> ¹	Two-striped sweetlips	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Labridae	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Mexican hogfish	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Labridae	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>	Humphead wrasse	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Labridae	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	Rockmover wrasse	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus olivaceus</i>	Longface emperor	Philippines	Sorgon and Abesamis 2023
<i>C. melampyngus</i>	Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus bohar</i>	Two-spot red snapper	Seychelles	Potts 1980

<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Mullidae	<i>Mulloidichthys flavolineatus</i> ²	Yellowstripe goatfish	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Mullidae	<i>Parupeneus cyclostomus</i> ³	Gold-saddle goatfish	Hawaii	Hobson 1974; Honebrink 2000
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Mullidae	<i>Parupeneus macronemus</i> ⁴	Long-barbel goatfish	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Muraenidae	<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Finespotted moray	Colombia	Quimbayo et al. 2014
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Muraenidae	<i>Gymnothorax griseus</i>	Geometric moray	Seychelles	Present study
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Muraenidae	Unidentified	Muraenid eel	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2019
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Scombridae	<i>Gymnosarda unicolor</i>	Dogtooth tuna	Seychelles	Potts 1981

Hunting by riding

<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Epinephelidae	<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i> ⁵	Pacific creole-fish	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2016
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Gerreidae	<i>Gerres oyena</i>	Common silver-biddy	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Mobulidae	<i>Mobula birostris</i> ⁶	Giant manta	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2016
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Monodactylidae	<i>Monodactylus argenteus</i>	Silver moony	Seychelles	Potts 1980
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Rhincodontidae	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Whale shark	Costa Rica	Auster et al. 2016
<i>C. melampygyus</i>	Scaridae	<i>Bolbometopon muricatum</i>	Green humphead parrotfish	Philippines	Sorgon et al. 2021*

*Nature of association speculated, not observed